

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF METAPHORICAL AND FIGURATIVE MEANINGS

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Annotation: The study employs a contrastive analysis approach to examine how metaphor and figurative language shape cultural perceptions and conceptual frameworks. Findings indicate that while universal cognitive mechanisms underlie metaphorical expressions, language-specific socio-cultural factors influence their semantic and pragmatic applications. The research contributes to cross-linguistic and intercultural studies, enhancing our understanding of metaphorization processes in different linguistic traditions.

Keywords: Metaphor, metonymy, figurative meaning, comparative linguistics, cultural perception, cross-linguistic analysis

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ МЕТАФОРИЧЕСКИХ И ПЕРЕНОСНЫХ ЗНАЧЕНИЙ

Аннотация: В данном исследовании применяется контрастивный анализ для изучения того, как метафоры и переносное значение формируют культурные представления и концептуальные модели. Результаты показывают, что, несмотря на наличие универсальных когнитивных механизмов, лежащих в основе метафорических выражений, их семантическое и прагматическое использование определяется языковыми и социокультурными факторами. Исследование вносит вклад в межъязыковые и межкультурные исследования, расширяя понимание процессов метафоризации в различных лингвистических традициях.

Ключевые слова: Метафора, метонимия, переносное значение, сравнительное языкознание, культурное восприятие, межъязыковой анализ.

There are two types of meanings in words. The first is called the original meaning, and the second is the figurative meaning. As for the first type of meaning, if the original meaning of a word means the same thing both when it appears alone

and when it appears in a text, it is called a word with its own meaning. If its meaning when it appears alone and its meaning in the text are two different things, then this word is used in a figurative meaning in the text. To the question of how we can find out whether a word is used in its own meaning and in a figurative sense, we answer this: it is very easy. We use the words in the text alone. As we said above, if a word in the text has the same meaning when it comes alone and in the text, it is used in its own meaning, or if it has a different meaning when it comes alone, it is used in a figurative sense. We can explain this to you with several examples. For example: Let's use the word "cold" alone in the sentence "Don't intend cold my friend" - the word "cold" is used in its own meaning when it refers to air and water. When the word "cold" appears in sentences with such combinations as "cold intention", "cold breath", "cold face", the word "cold" is used figuratively, going beyond its original meaning. The statement "My blood has enough iron" can be metaphorically interpreted as a declaration of vitality, resilience, and strength. Iron is essential for carrying oxygen, so a metaphorical "full iron" means the person has enough energy and resources to thrive. When the word "iron" is used alone, it means an iron, that is, an iron object, and it is not something to be in the blood. It means that this word has two different meanings when used alone and in the text, and is used figuratively in the text. Language is an integral part of human thought and culture, through which different layers of meaning are expressed. In particular, metaphorical and figurative meanings allow us to study the deep semantic properties of language units. These phenomena are especially vividly reflected in paremiological units - proverbs, sayings and other examples of folk wisdom. This study aims to conduct a comparative analysis of metaphorical and figurative meanings in English and Uzbek.

There are four types of meaning transfer methods: Metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche and function-relatedness. These are a sequence of meaning transfer methods. In addition, there are also types of meaning transfer such as irony and allusion. "Metaphor is a literary concept that uses the properties of another object in order to explain something or an action," says John Stephen. Metaphora- metaphora means "copy". The transfer of meaning based on the external similarity, formal, internal signs of an object, thing, or event is called a metaphor. More external similarity is called a metaphor. In the metaphorical method, the transfer of names occurs according to the relative similarity between objects and phenomena, and their color, shape, movement take the name of the second such object sign. With this method, the general concept of the sign is preserved for the transfer of meaning. For example, "black intention" in this case, the transfer of meaning is observed in the

word black. If it were a black pen, it would have its own meaning, and since the black color is likened to the bad intention inside, the meaning is transferred in the metaphorical method.

Metaphorical meaning arises as a result of the fact that words or expressions deviate from their direct lexical meaning and are associated with other concepts. This phenomenon is widespread in both languages and is inextricably linked with the historical experience, worldview and culture of the people. In Uzbek, the proverb “one who drinks sour yogurt with a burnt mouth” means caution, while the English phrase “Once bitten, twice shy” expresses the same idea.

The relevance of the research is that the study of the semantic properties of metaphorical units in English and Uzbek is of great importance not only from the point of view of linguistics, but also from the point of view of translation studies and cultural studies. This work aims to conduct a comparative study of metaphorical and figurative meanings in the paremiological system of both languages, identify their similarities and differences, and reveal problems in the translation process.

Questions and tests that ask us to find figurative words have been bothering us since we were students. There are many such questions in the “Agency for assessment of knowledge and competences under the ministry of higher education ,science and innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan” tests, so it is important for us to learn figurative words and their types thoroughly.

The comparative study of metaphorical and figurative meanings is an important scientific direction for linguistics, translation studies, and cognitive sciences, and its relevance and novelty are reflected in the following:

1. Revealing the interrelationship between language and thought - How metaphors are formed in different languages as a product of human thought and their relationship with cultural factors are studied.

2. The importance of comparative analysis - Difficulties encountered in translation processes are analyzed by identifying similar and different aspects of metaphorical meanings in different languages.

3. Analysis based on corpus linguistics and cognitive approaches - Metaphors are studied using modern technologies, artificial intelligence, and

automated analysis methods, creating an opportunity to determine how they are used in a real language environment.

4. Psycholinguistic and neurolinguistic studies - How metaphors affect the human mind, the mechanisms of their understanding and perception are studied in depth.

Conclusion

The comparative study of metaphorical and figurative meanings serves to create important scientific innovations not only in linguistics, but also in the fields of cultural studies, translation studies, and psychology. Therefore, research on this topic is of great theoretical and practical importance.

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